

External Validity: Code Book

Definitions

Observational research derives knowledge from observations rather than logical derivation on the basis of a theory. We distinguish three types of observational research as defined below.

Empirical research derives knowledge solely from observation.

Experimental research derives knowledge from observing effects on dependent variables upon alteration of independent variables.

Case Studies derive knowledge from selective observations (either empirical or experimental) of few individual subjects.

External Validity measures to what extent it is possible to generalize the findings, and to what extent the findings are of interest to other people outside the investigated case. During analysis of external validity, the researcher tries to analyze to what extent the findings are of relevance for other cases. (Wohlin et al. 102)

Internal Validity examines causal relations. It is “concerned with the validity within the given environment and the reliability of the results. Threats to internal validity are influences that can affect the dependent variable with respect to causality, without the researcher’s knowledge. Thus they threaten the conclusion about a possible causal relationship between treatment and outcome.” (Wohlin et al. 82,102, 133)

Construct Validity “reflects to what extent the operational measures that are studied really represent what the researcher has in mind and what is investigated according to the research questions.” (Wohlin et al. 102)

Open-Card Sorting

Card sorting is a research method in which study participants place individually labeled cards into groups according to criteria that make the most sense to them. In an open card sort, participants create and label their own groups of cards without predefined categories. In a closed card sort, the participants are provided a set of categories and are asked to slot content into those categories. In a hybrid card sort, participants start from a provided set of categories, which they can extend by additional categories as needed.

The following code book is intended to serve as the basis for a hybrid card sort.

Code Book

Classification Criteria for Observational Research

Case Study:

- The authors explicitly describe their work as “case study” AND
- The subject population is indeed small (5 or less).
- The research doesn’t include any intervention or alteration of observed variables.

Experimental:

- The authors report on the effects of a change they make (e.g., alteration of an algorithm) on some response variable(s) (e.g., execution time, memory consumption, number of found/localized/repaired defects) or on the effects of exposing a developed system to predefined execution conditions.

Empirical:

- The authors report the prevalence/distribution of properties (e.g., code size, programming language, defect density) across a population sample without any voluntary changes beyond what is necessitated by observation.

Label Taxonomy and Explanations

General Guide To Labeling:

Follow these guidelines when labeling the External Threats to Validity discussion from the paper:

1. Define the [Structural Properties](#) for the ETTV discussion
2. Determine the [Study Type](#)
3. Choose a fitting label from the selection of [ETTV factors](#) that best describes the argument in the ETTV discussion
4. Choose a fitting label from the selection of [Mitigation Strategies](#) that best describes the argument in the ETTV discussion
5. Determine the [Mitigation Level](#)

We have standardized our taxonomy of labels from a long list of possible labels suggested by previous labelers and we believe this taxonomy will be enough to cover the vast majority of cases you will encounter while labeling. Please take the time to read and understand the descriptions of each label. Depending on the excerpt you’re working with, you might end up having multiple labels on ETTV factors but no labels on mitigation strategies, or only a few ETTV factors labels and many labels on mitigation strategies. This can sometimes happen as many aspects of what the authors write can be encompassed within a single label or the authors might mention many ETTV factors but not offer any mitigation strategies. We also have some

labels with subcategories, such as *Selection Bias* and “*Mitigative selection*” *Criteria*. You don’t always have to use a subcategory; as an example, if you spot a case of *Selection Bias*, as in what’s described in the excerpt fits the general description in this codebook, but it doesn’t fit any of the subcategories like *Data Source* or *Participant Bias*, you can label it without using a subcategory. When you use a subcategory, you should format it with the main label and a colon (ex. Selection Bias: Data Source), otherwise just the label itself.

Structural Properties of Threats to External Validity Discussions:

After extracting the excerpt relevant to External Validity, make sure to add labels that describe:

- 1- The section name that the excerpt is taken from,
- 2- If present, the subsection name that discusses External Validity inside the section
- 3- Phrases that are related to or clearly implicate External Validity. These phrases are meant to be helpful indicators while looking for excerpts regarding External Validity when the authors of the paper didn’t dedicate a specific section for External Validity Discussions. Please only use “Phrase” labels in case there is no section or subsection that clearly identifies a text passage as a threats to external validity discussion.

The following labels are examples from our taxonomy to provide guidance:

- Section: Implications, Application, and Threat
- Section: Discussion
- Section: Future Work
- Section: Further Analysis
- Section: Limitations and Threats to Validity
- Section: Experimental Setup
- Section: Experimental Procedure
- Subsection: External Threat
- Subsection: External Validity
- Subsection: Generalizability
- Subsection: Threats to Validity
- Phrase: Future Work
- Phrase: In the future
- Phrase: Further Experiment
- Phrase: Generalizability
- Phrase: Out of the scope of work
- Phrase: Real-world
- Phrase: Representative(ness)
- Phrase: (Broader) Applicability
- Phrase: Comprehensive(ness)

Study Types:

Please refer to [the definitions above](#) to determine the type of study.

- Empirical
- Experimental
- Case Study
- Empirical and Experimental

Threats to External Validity Factors:

- Selection Bias: Subjects with certain traits are over- or under-represented because of how a sample is drawn. Bias types observed so far:
 - Geographic Bias (Data is skewed by location)
 - Domain Level (Only certain problem domains are studied)
 - Data Source (Choice of dataset or benchmark restricts generalizability)
 - Classification Bias (Systematic errors in labeling or categorizing data)
 - Participant Bias (Selected participants are not representative of the target population)
 - Popularity Bias (Frequently occurring or popular items are overrepresented)
 - Open v. Closed Source (Only open- or closed-source systems are used, limiting generalizability)
 - (Programming) Language Bias (Only a single programming language is studied)
 - Platform Choice (Only certain libraries or tools are considered)
- Human subjectivity (Bias introduced by individual human judgment during data annotation or analysis)
- Evaluation Bias (Bias arising from how performance or results are measured or compared)
- Representativeness Issues
 - Limited Subject Complexity (Subjects studied are simpler than real-world cases)
 - Structural difference (The structure of studied data or systems differs from the real-world target)
 - Distribution Mismatch (Data distribution differs from the target domain)
 - Simulation Bias (Results may differ due to the use of simulated environments instead of real-world settings)
 - Sampling Coverage (Limited sample size or diversity reduces representativeness)
- Lack of Data Quality (Threats due to inaccuracies or incompleteness of the data)
- Resource-Constrained Scope (Study is limited by time, computational power, or personnel resources)
- Reliance on External Factors (Results depend on conditions outside the study's control)
- Trade-off Favoring Internal Validity (Study design prioritizes control and accuracy over real-world generalizability)

- Author misunderstandings (Occasionally, a misunderstanding from the authors complicates the assignment of a label. We have identified two recurring misunderstandings.)
 - Approach (Applicability of a proposed approach or tool to other subjects is discussed. This is a limitation of the presented approach, not a threat to the external validity of the study.)
 - Validity Type (Misunderstanding the type of validity threatened)

Threats to External Validity Mitigation Strategies:

- Sample Diversity: The authors argue that a sampling bias is mitigated, because their sample is diverse and, thus, contains subjects not affected by a potential bias.
- Adaptability: To overcome constraints of a presented approach to subjects with certain traits, the adaptability of the presented approach is used to argue that the approach may be applicable to subjects with other traits as well if modified (which is argued to be easy).
- “Mitigative selection” Criteria: The authors sample subjects according to criteria that are considered to counteract a specific potential bias. A (non-exhaustive) list of such criteria follows. We exemplify the respective arguments for the first two criteria.
 - (Tool/Method) Effectiveness: A specific tool or method is chosen for its previously documented effectiveness.
 - Popularity: Tools, Benchmarks, etc. are chosen, because they are widely used.
 - Quality: Some (possibly vague) high quality attribute has been guiding the choice.
 - State-of-the-art: Choice for novelty/contemporarity
 - Tool Maturity: Choice for maturity-induced quality (proven-in-use)
 - Unspecified: No further information on the selection criterion
 - Complexity coverage: Choice for diversity in complexity
 - Practical Use: Choice based on what is used in practice
 - Literature-backed Justification: The authors argue for relevance of a sample or choice via its usage in existing work.
- Large number/Scale: A large number of subjects is argued to support generalizability.
- Limited Threat Impact: A stated threat to external validity is stated to have limited impact on the generalizability of the presented results.
- Random Sampling: Randomness in sampling is argued to avoid systematic sampling bias.
- Real-world Sample: Having obtained a sample from the real world (in contrast to synthesizing data, benchmarks, etc.) raises expectations that results obtained on that sample also generalize to the real world.
- Representative Sample: The results are expected to generalize to a larger population that the investigated sample is representative for.
- Homogeneous Observations: Generalizability is assumed on the basis that observations across the entire sample were identical or similar. This includes arguments about high interrater agreement.

- Purposive Sampling: The restriction to a specific sample is justified by technical limitations of an approach or tool to be evaluated/used in the study.
- Abstract Representation: The study operates on some abstract representation of subjects, such that specific properties (that are abstracted from) do not matter. As a consequence, the obtained results should generalize to various manifestations of these properties.
- High domain coverage: The population (subjects, categories, ...), from which a sample is drawn, is covered to a large degree or even exhaustively.
- Out-of-sample evaluation: To assess a potential bias in the studied sample, the obtained results are additionally evaluated on subjects outside of the studied sample for result validation.
- Further Research: The authors refer to a future assessment whether the presented results generalize to other subjects or settings.
- Author misunderstandings (Occasionally, a misunderstanding from the authors complicates the assignment of a label. We have identified two recurring misunderstandings.)
 - Approach (Applicability of a proposed approach or tool to other subjects is discussed. This is a limitation of the presented approach, not a threat to the external validity of the study.)
 - Validity Type (Misunderstanding the type of validity threatened)

Mitigation Level:

- Full: All discussed ETTV factors have a corresponding mitigation discussion.
- Partial: Some but not all discussed ETTV factors have a corresponding mitigation discussion.
- None: None of the discussed ETTV factors have a corresponding mitigation discussion.
- Unclear

Human Subject Involvement:

- Study Involving Human Subjects
- Study Involving Digital Subjects
- Study Involving Both Human and Digital Subjects